

Chemical Examination of *Scoparia dulcis* (Linn): Part—I

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Scoparia dulcis Linn, belonging to the family Scrophulariaceae is a herb, distributed throughout India and reported in indigenous medicine. The roots and leaves of the plant are used as a cure for tooth-ache, blennorrhagia and stomach troubles¹. It was therefore, of interest to undertake the chemical investigation of the whole plant of *Scoparia dulcis*, since no investigation on it was recorded in literature. The present report relates to the isolation of hexacosanol, β -sitosterol and *d*-mannitol from the root bark of this plant.

The benzene extract on concentration under reduced pressure gave a pale yellow residue, which was dissolved in minimum amount of chloroform and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (80 g.) using light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°), benzene, chloroform and their mixtures as eluents. The benzene eluates furnished a white solid (0.04 g.) which on repeated crystallisation from acetone melted at 79–80°. (Found : C, 80.6; H, 13.6%. Calc. for C₂₆H₅₄O : C, 81.6; H, 14.1%). It developed no colouration with tetranitromethane. The compound was identified as hexacosanol by direct comparison (m.p. and m.m.p.). The identity was further confirmed by preparing its acetate, m.p. 64–65° and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of hexacosanyl acetate.

The unsaponifiable matter of the light petroleum extract of the roots on chromatography over a column of Brockmann alumina (100 g.) furnished a white solid which on repeated crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol (1 : 1 v/v) yielded needles (0.2 g.); m.p. 135–136°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –34° (chloroform). (Found : C, 83.1; H, 11.87%. Calc. for C₂₉H₅₀O : C, 84.1; H, 12.15%). The compound gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol, gave an acetate, m.p. 124–26° and a benzoate, m.p. 144°, was identified as β -sitosterol, by direct comparison with an authentic sample of sterol, its acetate and benzoate (m.m.p.)².

The dilute alcohol extract furnished a white crystalline solid. After crystallisation from aqueous methanol the compound (1.8 g.) melted at 165–166°. The substance behaved like a polyhydroxy compound towards the ceric ammonium nitrate and Dunstan's reagents. The aqueous solution of the substance was sweet in taste. The substance was identified as *d*-mannitol from mixed m.p. determination and comparison of chromatograms using butanol, ethanol, water (4, 1.1, 1.8) as solvent. The acetate of the compound and *d*-mannitol hexaacetate³ were identical, m.p., m.m.p. 122–230°. (Found : C, 48.67; H, 5.6%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₆O₁₂ : C, 49.7; H, 6%)⁴.

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